

WP1 Shared modelling framework and learnings

D1.2 – Description of scientific methods

Task 1.3 Methods for Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Tutorial – Including time-dependencies in the estimation of climate change (CC) midpoint scores of bio-based productions.

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PROJECTS DETAILS			
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This tiered approach is designed to help users getting familiar with a time-explicit LCA framework. LCA practitioners with no previous experience will find with Tier 1 steps a didactic, stepwise tutorial towards including temporal considerations in LCAs. LCA practitioners with previous experience on time-explicit system modelling are invited to reproduce their work with Tier 1 guideline, in order to facilitate the use of Tier 2 and 3 guidelines.

The proposed stepwise tutorial assumes that the current state of the LCI is not temporally explicit.

The following case study will be employed to illustrate each stage of the tutorials. The functional unit is the production, mounting, use and recovery of a 1m² insulating board. The material is partly made of a bio-based chemical extracted and refined from hardwood. Once mounted, the insulating board is operating for 50 years. After dismounting, 10% of the used board cannot be separated from other building materials and is sent to landfill; 45% is used as a fuel in a cement factory; and 45% is mechanically recycled into a new material. During biomass transformation into the target compound, by-products are valorized as fuel.

Step 1: Roughly define the time period of the main life cycle phases of the product system under study

A minimum requirement is to break down the life cycle of the product system under study into at least four main phases (Figure 1):

- Biomass sourcing:
- Production
- Use
- End-of-life

Figure 1 – Terminology for system boundaries to develop LCA of the bio-based sector

Whenever possible, a higher granularity of the life cycle phases is recommended. For example, ‘Biomass sourcing’ phase can be split into e.g. ‘land use change’, ‘biomass growth’, ‘logging’, and so on. The number of Life Cycle stage is not limited here.

Cradle-to-gate studies are strongly advised to define at least two contrasted scenarios for the Use and End-of-Life phases (see ‘ALIGNED-T1.3-Guide on LCIA-CC’ document). Time-extended phases (such as biomass growth or landfiling) are simply modelled with start year and end year in Tier 1. The associated GHG flows are automatically approximated as a pulse emission occurring in the middle of the time interval.

An exemplary time-differentiation is presented for the afore-mentioned case study, with the following assumptions:

- Upstream temporal boundary of the system starts with hardwood harvest; this action is assigned reference year 0.
- Following a consequential approach, an increase in demand for hardwood will lead to an increase in demand for forest land, involving indirect Land Use Change – which is assumed here to occur 1 year following harvest.

- Forestry activity occurs *after* wood harvest. Indeed, hardwood forestry is performed as a response to an increase in demand for hardwood. Tree re-growth is assumed to last for 40 years.
- Collected hardwood is air-dried for several months. At year 1, it is processed with a biorefinery.
- The biorefinery yields several valuable fractions. 60%w of the coproducts are used as fuel within the biorefinery or by other activities. 30%w of the coproducts are used as chemical feedstocks for other activities.
- The remaining 10%w of the coproducts is used to manufacture the insulating board. It is assumed that manufacturing occurs at year 2.
- The insulating board is mounted at year 3, and left operational for 50 years without any intervention.
- The used board is dismantled at year 53. While landfill decomposition is assumed to last for 80 years, energy recovery and mechanical recycling are assumed to occur at year 53 exclusively.

When the temporality of all life cycle stages is set up, it is time to use the calculator. Open workbook file “ALIGNED-T1.3-CC calculator.xlsx” and go to ‘Tier1_Table’ sheet. Fill in Life cycle stage names, start years and end years. Table 1 provides an example related to the case study:

Table 1 – Example of time differentiation between the main life cycle phases of biobased production. Information labelled in blue is provided by the user; information in black is filled automatically.

Start year	End Year	Calendar period	Equivalent year	Year count	Life Cycle Stage
2026	2026	2026	2026	1	Land Use Change
2025	2066	2025 - 2066	2046	21	Forestry
2026	2026	2026	2026	1	Biorefinery
2026	2026	2026	2026	1	Use of coproducts
2027	2027	2027	2027	2	Insulating board production
2028	2028	2028	2028	3	Mounting
2028	2078	2028 - 2078	2053	28	Passive use
2078	2158	2078 - 2158	2118	93	EoL- landfill
2078	2078	2078	2078	53	EoL – cement factory
2078	2078	2078	2078	53	EoL – mechanical recycling

Step 2: Life cycle inventory of each life cycle phase

Based on Table 1, the user organizes GHG flows for each life cycle phase. The ALIGNED framework for time-explicit GHG accounting only considers CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O. Practitioners willing to include all GHGs and climate forcers are invited to use expert models such as CCI Tool¹.

In addition, following ALIGNED recommendations for biogenic carbon accounting, the user must compute separately biogenic and fossil carbon dioxide and methane, hence computing 5 different flows: CO_{2b}, CO_{2f}, CH_{4b}, CH_{4f}, N₂O (where _{-b} and _{-f} stand for biogenic and fossil, respectively).

¹ <https://www.insa-toulouse.fr/cci-tool/>

The aggregated net value for each substance over the entire duration of each life cycle phase is also reported in 'Tier1_Table' spreadsheet, following Table 2 format:

Table 2: Example of reporting time differentiated direct GHG emissions from the inventory of each life-cycle phase.

Life Cycle Stage	CO2_f	CO2_b	CH4_f	CH4_b	N2O
iLUC	5.94	12.3	0.0189	0.0222	0.0208
Forestry	0.623	-68.1	2.75E-03	2.29E-05	4.54E-05
Biorefinery	4.39	-0.042	0.0252	1.29E-04	3.15E-04
Use of coproducts	-25.9	52.4	-0.127	1.77E-03	2.69E-04
Insulating board production	2.61	0.0350	0.0151	7.35E-05	1.01E-04
Mounting	0.402	-1.52E-03	4.97E-04	-8.72E-07	1.08E-05
Passive use	0	0	0	0	0
EoL - landfill	0.0110	1.85E-05	8.84E-04	3.41E-08	2.02E-07
EoL - cement factory	1.28	-2.77E-04	-3.40E-03	-1.13E-05	1.28E-05
EoL - mechanical recycling	-0.589	2.70	-8.14E-05	-1.98E-04	3.59E-05

Note that not all LCA software can automatically deliver custom LCI results for each Life-Cycle phase. In this case, the user is invited to manually apply the following procedure:

1. duplicate existing LCIA method 'IPCC 2021 (incl. biogenic CO2) > climate change: total (incl. biogenic CO2) > global warming potential (GWP100)' into a new method (named e.g. GHG inventory)
2. remove all GHG flows other than CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O. There should remain 35 elementary flows (see Table 3 below).
3. convert all Characterization Factors to 1 for emissions to air and -1 for natural resources from air and emissions to soil (i.e. CO₂ uptake)
4. split the 35 elementary flows into 5 sub-categories: CO2f; CO2b; CH4f; CH4b; N2O.

LCIA calculation with this method should now deliver the expected outcome, which can be directly used to feed ALIGNED tool.

Table 3: list of elementary flows of custom LCIA method for time-explicit CC impact assessment

Impact category	elementary flow	category	Amount (kg)
CO2f	Carbon dioxide, fossil	('air', 'low population density, long-term')	1
		('air', 'lower stratosphere + upper troposphere')	
		('air', 'non-urban air or from high stacks')	
		('air', 'urban air close to ground')	
		('air')	
CO2b	Carbon dioxide, from soil or biomass stock	('air', 'low population density, long-term')	1
		('air', 'non-urban air or from high stacks')	
		('air', 'urban air close to ground')	
		('air')	
	Carbon dioxide, non-fossil	('air', 'low population density, long-term')	1
	('air', 'non-urban air or from high stacks')		
	('air', 'urban air close to ground')		

		('air')	
	Carbon dioxide, in air	('natural resource', 'in air')	-1
	Carbon dioxide, non-fossil, resource correction	('natural resource', 'in air')	-1
	Carbon dioxide, to soil or biomass stock	('soil', 'agricultural')	-1
		('soil', 'forestry')	
		('soil', 'industrial')	
		('soil')	
CH4f	Methane, fossil	('air', 'low population density, long-term')	1
		('air', 'non-urban air or from high stacks')	
		('air', 'urban air close to ground')	
		('air')	
CH4b	Methane, from soil or biomass stock	('air', 'low population density, long-term')	1
		('air', 'non-urban air or from high stacks')	
		('air', 'urban air close to ground')	
		('air')	
	Methane, non-fossil	('air', 'low population density, long-term')	1
		('air', 'non-urban air or from high stacks')	
		('air', 'urban air close to ground')	
		('air')	
N2O	Dinitrogen monoxide	('air', 'low population density, long-term')	1
		('air', 'non-urban air or from high stacks')	
		('air', 'urban air close to ground')	
		('air')	

Step 3: Tier1 GWP Scores from the ALIGNED tool

Go to 'Tier1_detailed_results' spreadsheet. It contains detailed midpoint scores for each GHG at each Life Cycle Stage, for the 4 calculation methods:

- ✓ GWP100 Levasseur method² (columns C:G);
- ✓ GWP500 Levasseur (columns H:L);
- ✓ GWP100 IPCC (i.e. time-invariant, -1/+1 approach), columns M:Q;
- ✓ GWP500 IPCC (columns R:V).

The coloured data bar in each cell shows the relative importance of the cell midpoint score, so that the reader can quickly grasp hotspots.

- Comparison between calculation methods

In columns W:AF, the relative difference between Levasseur and IPCC results is calculated for each GHG, LC stage and Time Horizon.

Dark-blue coloured cells indicate where the largest differences appear. For GHG [i] in Life Cycle stage [j], the relative difference is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta_{i,j} = \left| \frac{GWP_{Levasseur}(i,j) - GWP_{IPCC}(i,j)}{\sum_{i,j} GWP_{IPCC}(i,j)} \right|$$

In plain text, the midpoint score for each GHG and Life Cycle stage is compared between Levasseur and IPCC methods (with same time horizon), and their difference is scaled to the total IPCC midpoint score.

² Details on 'Levasseur method' can be found in the 'ALIGNED T1.3 Guide on LCIA-CC' report.

- Quick analysis

As a rule of thumb, large differences in results between GWP100 and GWP500 tend to indicate that CH₄ and/or N₂O play a prominent role; when differences are barely noticeable between time horizons, it means that CO₂ is the most important GHG to focus on.

Regarding the time dimension of the studied system, large differences can occur between Levasseur vs IPCC versions, in Life-Cycle stages with significant midpoint scores and a rather high 'Year count'. **In this case, the user is invited to fine-tune the temporality of such Life Cycle stages using Tier 2 calculator.**

Step 4: Tier2 - Fine-tune time-distribution of GHG flows

Step 4.1: prepare spreadsheet

- Go to spreadsheet 'Tier1_Table' and select all Life Cycle Stage names (cells F2 and downwards)
- Go to spreadsheet "Tier2-3_year_distribution", select cell C1, then right-click > Paste special > Transpose

The table in this spreadsheet now contains Life Cycle stages as column headers. This table can be now manually populated with the yearly distribution of GHG flows, for each Life Cycle stage.

Words of caution to fill the table:

- The total of each column needs to be 100%, for the calculation to work properly. There can be negative values in this table, but **the total of each column still needs to be +100%**.
- The total net amount of GHG flows can only be updated in spreadsheet 'Tier1_Table'
- There is only 1 possible time distribution for a Life Cycle stage. To discriminate time distribution among GHGs, it is possible to split a Life cycle stage into several parts (1 for each distinct time distribution), for example if CH₄ and CO₂ emissions are differently distributed during waste landfill. In this case, the operation should be done in Worksheet 'Tier1_Table' and then restart step 4.
- It is important to keep Life Cycle stage names rigorously identical between spreadsheets 'Tier1_Table' and 'Tier2-3_year_distribution'. Otherwise the calculation will not work properly.
- There is no automatic connection between Tier1 'calendar period' and Tier2 'time distribution'. This means that calendar periods defined in Tier 1 will not be considered anymore.

Some examples of typical yearly distribution of GHG flows, for different Life Cycle stage types:

- Manufacturing processes typically last less than 1 year, so the value of 100% can be assigned to the previously-defined reference year and the rest of the column is left empty.
- Long-lasting use phases can be considered as uniformly distributed (e.g. 2% of total emissions for a 50-year use phase).
- 'Unforced' decomposition e.g. in landfill could be considered with a decay function, for instance linear or first-order exponential decay.
- For forestry products (long-rotation crops), the user is invited to refer use 'ALIGNED-T1.2-LCA-Carbon-Flux-model.xlsx'.

Step 4.2: compute yearly impacts.

When the table is consistently populated, go to Data > Refresh all. Tier 2 and Tier 3 results will be computed simultaneously. NB: shortcut for 'Refresh all' is Ctrl + Alt + F5 or AltGr + F5.

Spreadsheets 'Tier2-3_LCI' and 'Tier2-detailed_results' display intermediary calculations:

- 'Tier2-3_LCI' lists flows of each GHG (in kg), for each Life Cycle stage and each calendar year.
- Tier2-detailed_results list the same flows but expressed in kg CO₂eq – using Levasseur methods for GWP100 and GWP500.

These tables can be used by advanced users for specific analyses.

Step 4.3: results analysis.

Spreadsheet 'Tier2_cumulated_GWP' displays the cumulative GWP scores over time. The user is invited to adjust chart axes bounds for smoother analysis. This chart hopefully serves as a visual tool to identify the influence of each Life Cycle stage on the overall midpoint score. The total GWP score can be read at the far-right of the chart and at the bottom of columns B and C.

As a rule of thumb, the closer an emission is to Time Horizon, the smaller its contribution to the midpoint score. Therefore, the GWP100 curve looks 'flattened' as compared to the GWP500 curve.

'Net-Zero GHG' year can be visually read on this chart ; Net-Zero year is likely to depend on the chosen time horizon (i.e. different Net-Zero years for GWP100 and GWP500 indicators), especially if CH₄ and N₂O emissions are significant.

Step 5: Tier3 – Temperature-change based indicators

Tier 3 results are automatically computed along with Tier 2 results. In Tier 3, other indicators than GWPs are used: GMTC and iGMTC (see 'ALIGNED-T1.3-Guide on LCIA-CC' document). Both indicators are computed using AGTP functions of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O. More details on the mathematical formulation of AGTP functions and use are available in 'ALIGNED-T1.3-Appendix_Tier3_math_model' document³.

NB: AGTP is not, contrary to AGWP, a time-integrated impact CF: AGTP is a time-response function from a pulse GHG flow. In other terms, AGTP translates the evolution of temperature change over time as a response to a pulse emission.

When combining the AGTP response for all GHG flows emitted each year of the studied system, one can calculate the induced temperature change every year if the future. This response function is the GMTC curve, shown in the left axis and expressed in Δ°C over time for a given functional unit.

iGMTC (right vertical axis) shows the cumulative temperature change, which represents the heat cumulated over time by the earth system.

NB: it is recommended to manually adjust maxima and minima for both left- and right- axes, to make sure their 0 are aligned.

³ See also: Tiruta-Barna, Ligia. 2021. 'A Climate Goal-Based, Multicriteria Method for System Evaluation in Life Cycle Assessment'. *Int J LCA* 26 (10): 1913–31. doi.org/10.1007/s11367-021-01991-1

Rules-of-thumb for interpreting GMTC and iGMTC results:

- GMTC and iGMTC results are expressed in physical units (resp. °C and °C.yr). They can be preferred to relative metrics (e.g. kg CO₂ equivalents) for practitioners interested in physical consequences of climate change. The behaviour of temperature increase over time leads to diverse cause-effect chains on ecosystems and societies, with different time scales and mechanisms. Although real impact cannot be reduced to a single chart, comparing the response of GMTC between 2 systems delivering the same functional unit can provide a finer interpretation of LCA results than a single midpoint result.
- The slope of GMTC curve close to current year (generally considered as reference year or year 0) indicates the rate of temperature change; faster temperature increase is likely to be more impactful to ecosystems, where slow-adapting species play a key role (eg wooden species)
- The maximum temperature change (i.e. the max value reached by GMTC curve) is an indicator related to the increase in the frequency and magnitude of extreme weather events such as heat waves, hurricanes, flooding.
- Long-term temperature change indicates the magnitude of required adaptation to climate change
- When GMTC reaches zero, the temperature-change neutrality of the studied functional unit is reached.
- iGMTC represents the heat accumulated over time by the atmosphere. It indicates the magnitude of effects on energy buffers of the climate system such as ice sheets, glaciers and oceans.
- Higher long-term iGMTC value indicate higher ice melt and higher sea level rise
- When iGMTC reaches zero, the cumulated heat neutrality of the studied functional unit is reached, meaning that long-term damages of climate changes are annihilated.
- It is important to bear in mind that time-explicit results are shown for a single functional unit located in time. Adaptation of the model and the resulting indicators are necessary, to assess the impacts of a recurrent activity such as reproducing the same functional unit every year during e.g. 20 years.

Complementary information on AGTP functions:

The Tier 3 calculator is a simplified version of the CCI Tool (see footnote 1), developed at INSA Toulouse and recently updated in the LCA4Bio project.

The Appendix document details the simplified mathematical model used here. Simplifications include:

- Only CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O gases are included, whereas CCI Tool includes other GHGs and short-lived climate forcers
- Fossil and non-fossil methane are not differentiated (i.e. the contribution to methane-emission metrics from CO₂ from fossil methane oxidation is not accounted)
- The AGTP function of a gas is computed independently from the other GHG emission profiles, whereas CCI tool includes the dynamic interactions between all climate forcers.

Practitioners willing to go beyond Tier 3 are invited to use CCI tool.